

1 **Methodology for determination of radon prone areas combining the definition of a**
2 **representative building enclosure and measurements of terrestrial gamma**
3 **radiation.**

4 *C. Briones¹, J. Jubera², H. Alonso³, J. Olai², J.T. Santana², N. Rodríguez-Brito², A. Tejera³, P.*
5 *Martel³, E. González-Díaz¹, J.G. Rubiano^{*3}*

6
7 ¹ *Dpto. de Técnicas y Proyectos en Ingeniería y Arquitectura de la Universidad de La Laguna,*
8 *38204. Canary Islands, Spain*

9 ² *Servicio de Laboratorios y Calidad de la Construcción del Gobierno de Canarias. 38107. Ca-*
10 *nary Islands, Spain*

11 ³ *Dpto. de Física. Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, 35017. Canary Islands, Spain*

12
13 * Corresponding Author: e-mail: jesus.garciarubiano@ulpgc.es

14
15 To be submitted to Science of the Total Environment

16
17 *Abstract—The recommendations of the European Atomic Energy Community (EURATOM) have recently*
18 *been incorporated into Spanish regulations in the Basic Document of Health Standards of the Technical*
19 *Building Code (CTE), section HS6, on protection against radon exposure. This further accentuates the need*
20 *to delimit radon prone areas as a strategy to address measures which minimise the effects of this gas on*
21 *the population. In this research, measurements of terrestrial gamma radiation and indoor radon of dwell-*
22 *ings have been carried out in the same location to delimit these risk areas. A new methodology has been*
23 *developed including a definition of a Representative Building Enclosure (RBE) and it is proposed a Build-*
24 *ing Storey Index (I_{BS}) which allows normalizing measurements of indoor radon activity concentration taken*
25 *in different levels from the ground to the RBE. The results show the need to consider the type of contact*
26 *that exists between the building and the ground as a determining factor of radon risk. Terrestrial gamma*
27 *radiation is used as a proxy for radioisotopic composition of soils to characterize the indoor radon risk at*
28 *different geological formation.*

29

30 *Keywords—Indoor radon; Terrestrial gamma radiation; Environmental radioactivity; Radon prone area;*
31 *Building type*

32 **1 INTRODUCTION**

33 Under normal conditions, ^{222}Rn from the ^{238}U decay chain constitutes the largest source of natural expo-
34 sure for human beings (50% of total natural radiation). The danger of exposure to high concentrations of
35 radon does not come from the gas itself, but from its short term decay products that are alpha particles
36 emitting elements in solid phase (^{218}Po , ^{214}Pb , ^{214}Bi and ^{214}Po). These products, whether free or attached to
37 atmospheric aerosols, have a high probability of disintegrating in the human lungs before being eliminated,
38 increasing the risk of cancer (Health Protection Agency, 2009). Exposure to radon occurs mainly by inha-
39 lation in poorly ventilated rooms, but radon and its products can also be assimilated by ingestion, either
40 dissolved in water or through the consumption of vegetables and most notably tobacco. In consequence,
41 long-term exposure to high concentrations of indoor radon (^{222}Rn) constitutes a public health problem.
42 Radon has been categorised as a Class 1 carcinogenic agent by the International Agency for Research on
43 Cancer (IARC) because it is the second most important cause of lung cancer after tobacco. The World
44 Health Organization (WHO) asserts that long-term exposure to high levels of radon concentration is closely
45 correlated to lung cancer according to several epidemiological studies. They urge institutions to take
46 measures in order to limit radon concentration levels in buildings to minimise the exposure of the population
47 (World Health Organization, 2015).

48 To mitigate the negative impacts of public exposure to high levels of radon concentration, Directive
49 2013/59 / EURATOM of the Basic Safety Standard (BSS) of the European Union (EU) established that
50 ‘Member States shall establish a national action plan that addresses long-term risks from exposure to radon
51 in homes, buildings with public access and workplaces for any source of radon entry, whether from soil,
52 building materials or water’. This directive suggests corrective measures which minimise indoor radon gas
53 concentration and a reference level of 300 Bq/m^3 of radon concentration is established. In December 2019,
54 RD 732/2019 which modifies the Technical Building Code (CTE) was passed in Spain. It was a transposi-
55 tion of the European directive and it supposes a new Section HS6 in the Basic Document of Health Stand-
56 ards of the CTE (Ministerio de Fomento, 2019) on Protection from Radon Exposure. This section, apart
57 from confirming the reference level of 300 Bq/m^3 , includes a national map establishing municipal risk

58 zones. However, it is pending approval through the ‘Real Decreto por el que se aprueba el Reglamento
59 sobre protección de la salud contra los riesgos derivados de la exposición a las radiaciones ionizantes’
60 (Ministerio de Presidencia y Administraciones Territoriales, 2018), which establishes control criteria in and
61 a maximum level of radon concentrations.

62 To apply this legislation in a territory, it is necessary to identify radon prone areas defined as those where
63 the probability of finding high activity concentration of indoor radon is above a determined limit. This
64 would allow a good assessment of the radon risk for a population in order to establish priority action areas.
65 It has been necessary to establish maps where radon-prone areas are defined in order to achieve the goals
66 established by the European Directive and national regulations. Different approaches are being used to
67 establish the radon-prone areas of determined geographical zones (García-Talavera and López-Acevedo,
68 2019):

- 69 • Direct measurement of Indoor Radon Concentration (IRC) by placing alpha track detectors in build-
70 ings.
- 71 • Indirect methods based on variables correlated to radon like radon gas from soils (Kemski et al.,
72 2001; Barnet and Fojtíková, 2008), gamma radiation (García-Talavera et al., 2013) or the uranium
73 content of rocks (Arnedo et al., 2017a; Ielsch et al., 2010).
- 74 • Hybrid methods which combine direct measurements with geological or radiological variables
75 (Kemski et al., 2009; Cinelli et al., 2011).

76 In Spain, the Nuclear Safety Council (CSN) has employed two defined strategies to develop an indoor
77 radon risk map of the Canary Islands (García-Talavera and López-Acevedo, 2019). However, they did not
78 adopt the strategy realised for the mainland map, not taking into account the analysis based on gamma
79 radiation data from Project MARNA (Suárez-Mahou et al., 2000). This was possible given the higher den-
80 sity of indoor radon measurements available in the islands. Six of the eight islands (with lower populations)
81 were identified as non-priority action areas because the available measurements were sufficiently below
82 the reference level. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that the western islands have significantly
83 lower number indoor radon measurements than the eastern islands. The main islands (Tenerife and Gran
84 Canaria) have been analysed by grouping areas according to the chemical composition of lithostratigraphic
85 units of islands (García-Talavera and López-Acevedo, 2019) and applying statistical criteria developed by
86 Garcia-Talavera San Miguel et al. (2013).

87 Section HS6 of the Basic Document of Health Standards of CTE is based on the methodology and results
88 shown in the work of García-Talavera and López-Acevedo (2019). It classifies Spanish municipalities into
89 two levels according to their radon risk potential: zone I (moderate risk) and zone II (high risk). In Tenerife
90 and Gran Canaria (Canary Islands, Spain), 50 of 52 municipalities are in zone II. Thus 99.4% of the whole
91 population of both islands (83.8% of the population of the Canary Islands) would be affected by the
92 maximum risk level established by regulation, so that, among other requirements, an additional system like
93 a ventilated containment space or ground depressurisation system will be required for new buildings from
94 the approval date.

95 This paper presents the methodology followed to determine the radon-prone areas in two municipalities of
96 the Tenerife and Gran Canaria islands, belonging to the Spanish archipelago of the Canary Islands.

97 This work is structured as follows. In section 2, we will describe the factors which our research is based
98 on. In section 3, the geology of the area of study will be presented in detail. The instrumentation and
99 methods adopted during the measurement campaigns are reported in section 4. Section 5 is devoted to the
100 results of our study, including the treatment of statistical uncertainties. Finally, conclusions are drawn in
101 section 6.

102 **2 FACTORS INFLUENCING IRC**

103 Indoor radon levels are a function of several factors: geology of the area, taking into account the activity
104 concentration of ^{226}Ra of different types of rocks which is the immediate origin of ^{222}Rn in the disintegration
105 chain; the permeability of the ground which is closely correlated with transport and entry of radon into
106 buildings (Font, 1997); building typology, including building material and the permeability of the envelope
107 of the building in contact with the ground (Frutos Vázquez, 2009); the presence and type of basement or
108 chamber below the house; factors like atmospheric pressure or temperature which allow a dominant driving
109 force for radon entry according to differential pressures (Hintenlang and Al-ahmady, 1992); and domestic
110 lifestyles. These factors can be divided into intrinsic permanent (a) and extrinsic variable (b) factors:

111 a) *Intrinsic permanent factors:*

112 - Natural: geology (the radon strength of the soil).

113 - Permeability of the envelope of the building in contact with the ground.

114 b) *Extrinsic variable factors:*

115 - Natural: weather and climate factors.

116 - Artificial: ventilation of the building enclosure depending on the habits of the occupants.

117 This work will be focused on studying the influence of intrinsic permanent factors in the presence of indoor
118 radon, such as the characteristics of soils and rocks that buildings sit on and the typology of the building
119 and level of contact with the ground.

120 **3 GEOLOGY OF THE AREA OF STUDY**

121 The Canary archipelago has a volcanic origin with geological formations over 30 million years old and
122 it extends to approximately 500 km.

123 The volcanic rocks of the Canary Islands belong to the alkaline igneous series, in this case, associated
124 intraplate volcanism (Carracedo et al., 2002). This igneous series is formed by a sequence of rocks whose
125 composition evolves from undifferentiated terms represented by basalts, intermediate terms represented by
126 trachybasalts, and finally differentiated terms represented by trachytes and phonolites. In order to analyse
127 the relationship between the geology and concentration of radon activity in the soils, a simplified classifi-
128 cation, based on the geochemistry characteristics and radiological behaviour of rocks in the Canary Islands
129 has been elaborated, and is detailed in Table 1.

130

Table 1. Simplified classification of the soils of the Canary Islands based on radiological and geochemical criteria (Arnedo et al., 2017)

Code A	<i>Intermediate and acidic rock</i> (trachytes, phonolites, rhyolites, trachybasalts, benmoreites, syenites, sieno-diorite, nefelític syenite)
Code B	<i>Ultrabasic and basic rock</i> (basanites, basalt olivine, basalt pyroxenic, basalt plagioclastic, nephelinites, hawaitas, tephrites, mugaritas, phonolitic tephrites, tephrites phonolites, peridotite: dunites, werlites, lerzolites, piroxenites, olivine gabbro, feldspar gabbros, noritas, ijolites)
Code C	<i>Terrestrial detrital sediments</i> (clay, silt)
Code D	<i>Marine detrital sediments</i> (silt, sand and gravel-edge-blocks in submerged areas, beaches and dunes)

131 This classification is based on that established by (Arnedo et al., 2017) for the Canary Islands. In their
132 paper, Arnedo et al. study the content of natural radioisotopes (^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K) and they determine
133 that the intermediate or acidic rocks (Code A in the present classification) are those that present a higher

134 concentration of natural radioisotopes and, in particular, of ^{226}Ra which is the parent nucleus of ^{220}Rn . In
135 contrast, the work of Arnedo et al., (2017) shows that the basic and ultrabasic rocks (Code B in the present
136 classification), which make up most of the territory of the Canary Islands, present reduced concentrations
137 of natural radioisotopes and of ^{226}Ra in particular. The difference between the radiological behaviour of
138 both codes is observed regardless of whether the rocks are plutonic or volcanic and, for this reason, in the
139 simplified classification of this paper, they are treated jointly in each code. The classification is completed
140 with category C dedicated to terrestrial sediments that mainly encompasses the clays and silts and category
141 D assigned to marine sediments, mainly beach sands.

142 It is important to note that in the case of the Canary Islands, soils are poorly developed and are
143 fundamentally composed of the type of rocks abundant in their local environment. For this reason, when
144 we study an area and classify it as A and B, it means that the dominant rocks and soils derived from their
145 weathering correspond to these geochemical/radiological categories that we have established. Clays will
146 also be different depending on whether they are acidic or basic in composition, but due to their
147 characteristics of accumulating elements of large ionic radius, they always present a higher concentration
148 of natural radioisotopes than the rocks of their surrounding environment from which they come (which can
149 be either acidic or basic) and therefore have a different code.

150 The lithological map of the Canary Islands is characterised by having great heterogeneity in a relatively
151 small space. In addition, it is sometimes made up of layers of reduced thickness, with underlying layers of
152 different composition. There is an added difficulty in identifying the soil due to the proximity of the edges
153 of different lithologies or the carrying out of excavations that allow reaching a layer with characteristics
154 different from the outer layer. In order to minimise the aforementioned edge effect, soils have been
155 identified by measuring terrestrial gamma radiation (TGR), which allows us to assign the analysed points
156 to a specific code.

157

158 This paper studies the radon exposure risk in San Cristóbal de La Laguna and Telde (second municipal-
159 ities in order of population for the main islands of the archipelago, Tenerife and Gran Canaria respectively).
160 These municipalities were selected because both are classified as zone II for radon risk (Ministerio de
161 Fomento, 2019) and have similar characteristics (Table 2). Furthermore, both municipalities have most of
162 their geology (volcanic rocks) involve by the TAS diagram (Total Alkali Silica) (R. W. Le Maitre, 2002)

163 which classifies volcanic rocks based on the relation between alkaline minerals content (Na_2O and K_2O)
164 and silicates content (SiO_2).

Table 2. Geographical characteristics of study areas

	San Cristóbal de La Laguna	Telde
Location	NE Tenerife	E Gran Canaria
Area (km²)	102.60	102.43
Elevation (masl)	1020	1546
Population density (people per km²)	1551.07	1024.52

165

166 It is necessary to highlight the geological singularity of the municipality of San Cristóbal de La Laguna.
167 Much of its geology is composed of basalts, and we can distinguish three different geological areas in the
168 municipality of La Laguna. The old Anaga Massif Structure located in the East – Northeast zone with
169 predominate basaltic flows and basanitic basaltic flows; the South and Northwest zone which is a younger
170 geological zone composed of basaltic flows; and a Central and Western zone with little difference in ele-
171 vation made up of soils formed by sandy clay deposits and lake soils. The last one has a particular geology
172 due to the existence of a lagoon (already disappeared in the mid-19th century), in addition to being an area
173 that, due to its rainy climatology, has led to the formation of fertile land of considerable size. The urban
174 area is sited on basic flows (Code B) and clayey soils (Code C).

175 Most of the area of the municipality consists of basic volcanic rocks and soil deposits (detrital sediments)
176 from these rocks in the area with lower elevation. These types of soils can be classified as Code B. However,
177 there are small located areas of intermediate/acid volcanic rocks (Code A), especially on the northern side,
178 but there are no urban areas there.

179 **4 INSTRUMENTATION AND METHODS**

180 *4.1 Gamma radiation rate measurement equipment*

181

182 Gamma radiation is considered in the literature as a proxy variable to estimate radon risk areas. The
183 Spanish maps of radon prone areas uses it as a categorical variable to exclude some areas (García-
184 Talavera and López-Acevedo, 2019). In this work, terrestrial gamma radiation is also explored as a
185 determining factor. The instrumentation used for measuring the external gamma dose rate was:

186

187 **Saphimo MiniTRACE CSDF** is a contamination monitor and multifunctional survey meter. It is provided
188 with an energy compensated Geiger-Mueller pancake detector with an active counter area of 15.5 cm² and
189 active diameter of 44.5 mm. For the measurement of ambient gamma radiation, the Rate Mean Mode is
190 used, which performs a temporal average of the measurements that allows reducing the error by increasing
191 the counting time. The uncertainty in the measurements was established to be lower than 10%, which
192 required a counting time of around 20 minutes. The detector provides the result of the energy compensated
193 to the ambient dose equivalent ($H^*(10)$) in microSv/h. The gamma sensitivity is 4.3 cps/ μ Sv/h and the
194 energy range runs from 26 keV to 1.25 MeV. The lower limit of detection is 0.01 μ Sv/h. A certificate of
195 calibration was provided by the supplier from October, 2018 and verified periodically.

196 **Ludlum μ R model 12S** is a radiometer equipped with 1" \times 1" sodium iodide (NaI)TI scintillation detectors.
197 This equipment is designed for environmental low-level gamma surveys and its typical sensitivity is 175
198 cpm/ μ R/h. The inherent detector background was determined from the measurements taken within a 15 cm
199 thick iron shield. It was calibrated in June 2020, before the measurement campaign, at the Spanish Center
200 for Energy, Environmental and Technological Research (Ciemat).

201

202 To relate the measurements of both detectors, an intercomparison curve with the distance from a standard
203 point source has been carried out according to the usual process. Using this curve (see figure 1),
204 measurements from the Geiger minitrace detector in μ Sv/h can be directly converted to the readings from
205 the Ludlum 12S radiometer in μ R/h. The final results are expressed in nGy/h using a factor 8.76 as
206 equivalence between μ R/h and nGy/h.

207

208 **Figure 1.** Intercomparison curve with the distance from a standard point source of both radiometers

209 *4.2 IRC measurement equipment*

210 As it is said above ^{222}Rn is a radioisotope in the decay chain of ^{238}U which decays into ^{218}Po by alpha
 211 emission of 5.59 MeV. Nuclear tracks detectors are a widely used method to obtain radon activity concen-
 212 tration in air. In this work, Radosys RSKS Type alpha-track detectors have been used to measure IRC.
 213 Each dosimeter is made up of a cylindrical plastic diffusion chamber containing a 100 mm² CR-39 chip.
 214 Typical detector equilibrium time is 3 h. They have a sensitivity of 2.0 tracks·cm²·kBq⁻¹·h⁻¹·m³ and a satu-
 215 ration limit greater than 12000 kBq/m³. The typical starting background of the detector is 0.3 tracks·mm⁻²
 216 and its detection limit is 6 Bq/m³ for 90 days of exposure. Etching is performed using a 25% /6.25 molar
 217 sodium-hydroxide solution at an Etching temperature of 90 centigrade with an Etching time of 4.5 hours.
 218 Two systems were used for processing the dosimeters: the Radosys NanoReader/NanoBath system located
 219 at the Laboratory and Construction Quality Service of the Ministry of Public Works and Transport of the
 220 Canary Islands Government on the Island of Tenerife; and the Radosys Radometer 2000/RadoBath system
 221 located at the Laboratory of Environmental Radioactivity of the Physics Department of the University of
 222 Las Palmas de Gran Canaria on the Island of Gran Canaria. Each batch of detectors used has individualised
 223 calibration parameters provided by the supplying company and updated in the control/reading software.

224 *4.3 Classification of building enclosures according to their level of contact with the ground*

225

226 Given the fact that radon flux penetrates into the building through the envelope from subsoil, it is reasonable
227 to highlight the importance of considering the contact level of the envelope of enclosures as a determinant
228 influence in IRC. For this purpose, a classification of buildings based on the contact level to the ground of
229 the lowest storeys has been designed distinguishing among five simplified types from A to E as shown in
230 Table 3.

231

232 Several researchers agree on the decision to take long-term measurements of radon on the ground floor
233 (floor of a building at ground level) or in those lowest floors of the building with a certain level of occupa-
234 tion, but without giving a special relevance to establishing some uniformity in the choice of the floor in
235 which measurements will be realised (Robayna Duque, 2002; Sainz-Fernandez et al., 2014; Collignan et
236 al., 2016). However, the most common tendency in Europe is taking indoor radon measurements on the
237 ground floor (Bossey, 2015; Elío et al., 2017). The Pan-European Map (Elío et al., 2019) proposes an
238 interesting specification to homogenise the way of treating data from all the participating countries in order
239 to elaborate a common indoor radon map. This map covers 50% of Europe with a 10 km x 10 km grid
240 containing the mean of the measurements from each cell from participating countries realised exclusively
241 on the ground floor of the studied buildings, regardless of whether it is in direct contact with the ground or
242 has one or more basement floors on the lower level.

243

244 One of the objectives of this work is to try to quantify in some way the significance of the results in the
245 way of choosing the enclosures in each building where such measurements should be taken. This is neces-
246 sary to propose a clear definition of a representative building enclosure and its behaviour against radon
247 concentration, where measurements have to be taken, that could be extended to the protocol of radon prone
248 areas research in other regions. We define as the **Representative Building Enclosure (RBE)**, the enclosure
249 located on the lowest floor at ground level which offers sufficient natural lighting and ventilation conditions
250 in order to be inhabited. Complementarily, in order to analyse the data obtained in this work, we define the
251 Upper and Lower **Adjacent Building Enclosure (ADE-U and ADE-L** respectively), as the enclosures
252 located immediately above RBE when there is no basement in the building, or the enclosure immediately
253 below RBE in other cases. (See Table 3).

254

255 Although the criterion followed by Elío et al. (2019) involves an important improvement to achieve a

256 procedural homogenisation, if the objective is characterising radon risk in different territories in a homo-
 257 geneous way, it is still possible to establish greater control over the variability of the boundary conditions
 258 that should be considered. By considering only ground floor results in order to map radon prone areas in
 259 Germany, Bossew realised an interesting comparison between results from ground floors of buildings with
 260 and without a basement (Bossew, 2015).

261

262 In this work, we wanted to take a further step in studying this effect by proposing a more specific cate-
 263 gorysation of ground floor enclosures in buildings. For this, two complementary categories of RBE have
 264 been considered based on the contact with the ground, so that Category I enclosures have a direct contact,
 265 whereas Category II enclosures have an interspace between the measured enclosure and the ground. Within
 266 Category II, if this interspace is constituted by a basement, the RBE is classified as Sub-category II-B,
 267 while to classify those RBE which have an air-chamber below the ground floor Sub-category II-AC is used.
 268 (See Table 3.)

269

Table 3. Distribution of RBE and ADE in the studied buildings and categorisation of RBE.

270

271 4.4 *IRC measurements campaign*

272

273 According to the described methodology, a total of 154 locations (85 from La Laguna and 69 from Telde)
274 have been investigated in this work (See figures 2 and 3). These buildings have been randomly selected to
275 perform long-term measurements of IRC using passive detectors. The aim is to achieve a distribution of
276 these points in the territory as uniformly as possible, as well as of a sufficient density to carry out an
277 adequate statistical study. This process provided a list of buildings with residential buildings predominating,
278 most of which are inhabited by a single family, although a certain number of buildings in the service sector
279 are also included.

280

281 In order to achieve the purposes of this work, it is necessary to analyse and try to quantify the capacity of
282 radon gas to distribute vertically between adjacent floors. For this reason, alpha track detectors were placed
283 on the two lowest floors of the buildings studied, where it was possible to measure on several floors
284 simultaneously. The protocol for the distribution of detectors in each building is as follows:

- 285 • In order to guarantee the quality of the measurement performed, duplicated detectors were placed
286 in RBE.
- 287 • Only one detector was placed on the upper (ADE-U) or lower (ADE-L) floor depending on the
288 case.

289

290 Next, we kept a check on the placement protocol, choosing the best situation and avoiding spaces with
291 draughts. Also, additional information was collected by using ad hoc sheets (identifiers for dosimeters, type
292 of building, year of construction, location, time of use, periods of occupation and perception of ventilation).
293 After a minimum period of three months, for the removal of detectors, a dosimeter wrapping protocol was
294 carried out to minimise possible contamination of the sample from the point of exposure to the laboratory.

295

296 4.5 *Radiation gamma measurements*

297

298 Measurements of the rate of exposure to gamma radiation were taken in areas of unbuilt terrain as close as
299 possible (not upper than 150 meters) to the buildings where IRC were obtained in the previous campaign,
300 as reported in figures 6a and 6b. Measurements were made one meter from the ground, with the objective

301 to determine the influence of the different lithologies of the ground in the different study areas. It has been
302 necessary to take various measurements in each location due to the statistical nature of the radiological
303 phenomenon. MARNA (Suárez-Mahou et al., 2000) recommends taking about five measurements at 5-
304 minute intervals, considering the average obtained from them as the definitive measurement. Even more
305 measurements were taken close to the boundaries of lithology change according to the geological map.

306

307 For this work, only external sources of gamma radiation were considered which come from the presence of
308 radioisotopes in the ground, building materials, water and air. The cosmic radiation component at the lati-
309 tude of Canary Islands was estimated using the equation considered in the work of Arnedo et al., (2017).

310

311 4.6 *Geoprocessing of the results*

312

313 An important tool to organise the results and additional data is the Geographic Information System (GIS).
314 It provides the possibility to introduce geological and geotechnical maps (lithological areas), and it facili-
315 tates the identification of abnormal behaviour of some results. The free and open-source cross-platform of
316 GIS Quantum GIS (QGIS) was used for this goal.

317 The maps used in this work have been obtained from Cartografía de Canarias S. A. (GRAFCAN) (Canary
318 Islands special data infrastructure of Canary Islands Government): IDECanarias Topographical Map
319 1:20.000, IDECanarias Geological Map, IDECanarias Geotechnical Map and IDECanarias Integrated
320 Topographical Map 1:5000.

321

322 4.7 *Upper tolerance bounds*

323

324 The criteria established by García-Talavera and López-Acevedo (2019) for the determination of the dif-
325 ferent radon-prone areas have been followed, as developed in the work of García-Talavera et al. (2013).
326 One of the most outstanding characteristics of indoor radon gas concentration is its great variability and
327 asymmetry. It is characteristic of a data set affected by random variables that follow a log-normal statistical
328 distribution, where x_g is the geometric mean and s_g is the geometric standard deviation (IGFAE, 2019).
329 Therefore, it can be affirmed that its logarithm ($y_i = \ln[x_i]$) follows a normal distribution. Accordingly,

330 the unilateral upper bound \tilde{Y}_p with a confidence level $100(1 - \alpha)\%$ that $100p\%$ of population where n
 331 samples come from at least for a normal distribution is given by Odeh and Owen (1980):

332

$$333 \quad \tilde{Y}_p = \bar{y} + g'_{(1-\alpha),p,n} \cdot S_y \quad (2)$$

334

335 where, \bar{y} is the arithmetic mean, $g'_{(1-\alpha),p,n}$ a factor tabulated by Odeh and Owen (1980) for the calculation
 336 of the upper tolerance bound in a normal distribution and S_y is the estimate of the population standard
 337 deviation given by equation 3:

338

$$339 \quad S_y = \sqrt{\frac{n}{n-1}} \cdot s_y, \quad (3)$$

340

341 where s_y is the standard deviation of the samples.

342

343 Finally, taking into account the equations derived from considering ($y_i = \ln[x_i]$), $x_g = e^{\bar{y}}$ y $s_g = e^{S_y}$
 344 the unilateral upper tolerance bound \tilde{X}_p with a confidence level of $100(1 - \alpha)\%$ that $100p\%$ of the population
 345 which the n data come from at least, for a log-normal distribution is given by:

346

$$347 \quad \tilde{X}_p = X_g \cdot (S_g)^{g'_{(1-\alpha),p,n}} \quad (4)$$

348

349 Therefore, the upper tolerance bound considered in this work (UTB), as indicated in the first paragraph,
 350 a value of $\alpha = 0.10$ and a value of $p = 0.90$, are considered, being able to obtain the values of
 351 $g'_{(1-\alpha),p,n}$ from tables included in Odeh and Owen (1980) and Meeker et al. (1991) for different values of n ,
 352 $(1-\alpha)$ and p . To handle a type II error, a sample size of $n \geq 27$ must be set (García-Talavera and López-
 353 Acevedo, 2019).

354

355 It is important to note that this statistical methodology applied to assess the risk of indoor radon in en-
 356 closures is sufficiently sensitive for the size of the sample and the deviation of the set. Given the high level
 357 of certainty required (90%), it happens that in the cases in which a population group with a small sample
 358 size is subjected to analysis, the characterisation value obtained is strongly penalised. In this sense, for

359 example, a sample of 27 values with a geometric mean of 70 Bq/m³ and a geometric deviation of 2.36
360 Bq/m³ corresponds to an estimate of its UTB of 300 Bq/m³ and keeping the same geometric mean and the
361 same deviation but with only 10 samples the UTB value is 413 Bq/m³. This means that a smaller sample
362 size reports higher UTB and small increases in its size cause significant reductions in the UTB obtained.
363 Nevertheless, when sample size starts to be enough, UTB trends to stabilise asymptotically. According to
364 this, García-Talavera et al. (2013) established in $n = 27$ a compromise sample size for which the effort spent
365 to increase the sample size is greater than its effect on the accuracy of the results. In those cases analysed
366 in this paper where the sample size is clearly lower than this reference value, as the comparison of UTB
367 among groups may be distorted by this circumstance, it has been preferred to use the geometric mean rather
368 than this parameter in the analysis of the results.

369 **5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

370 As already indicated above, this work aims to analyse the influence of *intrinsic permanent factors* when
371 radon prone areas are identified. Firstly, the typology of building has been studied, especially the level of
372 contact with the ground of enclosures studied, as a first attempt to highlight the importance of its weight on
373 the behaviour of IRC. Secondly, an analysis of the geology of both municipalities was carried out, using
374 radiometric tools in order to evaluate possible different indoor radon levels based on the composition of
375 soils where buildings sit.

376

377 *5.1 Lower and upper enclosures in the building*

378

379 Buildings for residential use, mostly single-family type, and service sector buildings were studied. These
380 buildings have been classified according to their typology following the five general types based on the
381 way that the building makes contact with the ground (See Table 3).

382

383 Measurements were recorded in the two lowest adjacent floors of the building if possible, provided that one
384 of them is in contact with the ground, according to the methodology. The lower building enclosure can be
385 located on the basement or ground floor depending on the existence of a floor below ground level. These
386 pairs of measurements per building can allow to distinguish a different indoor radon behaviour between
387 both adjacent enclosures.

388

389 Figure 2 shows results for lower floors and upper floors displayed in pairs in locations where both
390 measurements could be realised (78 buildings represented in abscissas). It enables the comparison of the
391 observed indoor radon results (Bq/m^3).

392

393

394

Figure 2. IRC results in lower and upper enclosures

395 As can be seen in figure 2, lower enclosures have a higher radon indoor level in most cases because of the
396 greater direct contact with the ground, being 64% of all cases. This supposes a significant difference
397 between geometric means being above 33% in the case of upper enclosures compared to lower enclosures
398 with the same geometric standard deviation ($s_g = 2.3$). Considering the upper type of enclosure in order to
399 characterise a building to estimate radon prone areas gave a UTB of $255 \text{ Bq}/\text{m}^3$ ($45 \text{ Bq}/\text{m}^3$ below 300
400 Bq/m^3) while if lower type results are considered UTB rises to $346 \text{ Bq}/\text{m}^3$ ($46 \text{ Bq}/\text{m}^3$ over reference level
401 $300 \text{ Bq}/\text{m}^3$).

402

403 Radon measurements for the two types of enclosures can be described by a lognormal distribution
404 (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test with Lilliefors correction, p -value = 0.20 for both lower and upper enclosures)
405 and Levene's test showed heterogeneous variances (p -value = 0.01). Thus, the application of the Mann-
406 Whitney U test shows a p -value = 0.05, which is in the limit of rejecting the null hypothesis. Thus, it is not
407 possible to conclude that there is a difference between the radon measurements of both lower and upper
408 enclosures. Therefore, it seems appropriate to bear this circumstance in mind when selecting the enclosures
409 in which the measurement is carried out, considering the difference that is observed between lower and

410 upper enclosures in the building given the influence they may have when estimating the values of UTB and
411 the geometric means of IRC in the characterisation of radon prone areas as it happens in our case.

412

413 On the other hand, there are few references to systematic studies that deal with the relationship between
414 radon concentration levels that can be obtained between building enclosures located on adjoining floors of
415 the same building. Only one document (European Commission, 2019) refers to the estimation of ratios
416 between floors without specifying the methodology followed to obtain them. These ratios establish the
417 relationship between the different floors of the building and the ground floor making use of IRC studies
418 developed in some European regions. From one of these studies (Bochicchio et al., 2005), the ratio is
419 calculated using the quotient between the arithmetic mean of the results obtained on each floor of the
420 buildings considered in the field campaign and that of those obtained on the total of the ground floors. The
421 contribution of this work to this line of research is that, having the pair of values obtained in the two lower
422 adjacent floors of each building studied, allows comparing pairs of data obtained under exactly the same
423 boundary conditions or, as we propose in this article, under the same intrinsic and extrinsic factors.

424

425 Table 4 shows a comparison between the ratios in different regions, verifying that the results obtained in
426 this work are close to the ranges of values obtained in other regions. In addition, this table includes the
427 basement / ground floor ratio, which has only been compared with the available data from Bochicchio et
428 al. (2005).

429

Table 4. Comparative among IRC ratios by storey levels from various researches

Region	Ratio Basement/Ground floor	Ratio Ground floor/first floor
Italy	1.2*	1.2
Barcelona (Spain)	--	1.6
Madrid (Spain)	--	1.5
UK	--	1.5
Austria (from 5 provinces)	--	1.5
This work	1.4	1.4

430 * Data obtained from (Bochicchio et al., 2005)

431

432 Considering this behaviour, this paper has determined an index with the aim to correct the lack of
 433 homogeneity due to the fact of choosing building enclosures with different levels of ground contact to
 434 characterise a determined area. This index allows to normalise values obtained in building enclosures
 435 located in different storeys with respect to the RBE in order to be considered in the process of elaboration
 436 of radon prone maps in determined study areas. For this purpose, a **Building Storey Index (I_{BS})** has been
 437 established, which is defined according to expression 5.

438

$$439 \quad I_{BS}(i) = \frac{\langle IRC_{RBE} \rangle_{GM}}{\langle IRC_i \rangle_{GM}} \quad (5)$$

440

441 Where IRC_{RBE} is the IRC in the representative building enclosure and IRC_i is the IRC in a building
 442 enclosure located in a determined storey different to RBE where I_{BS} is to be calculated.

443

444 In order to obtain this expression, the distribution of the set of IRC_{RBE} has been studied, which is adapted
 445 to a log-normal distribution, considering the normal distribution of its transformed values (natural logarithm
 446 of IRC_{RBE}). In the same way, we have taken the values of IRC in upper and lower adjacent building
 447 enclosures separately (IRC_{ADE-U} and IRC_{ADE-L}) and it has been proved that its transformed values also
 448 conform to a normal distribution. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to the transformed data with a level
 449 at decision of 5% of IRC_{ADE-L} ($p = 0.67$), and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for transformed values of IRC_{ADE-}
 450 U ($p = 0.56$) and IRC_{RBE} ($p = 0.93$). Considering the log-normal distribution of the values of IRC, it is
 451 inferred that the geometric mean is the statistical mean which adjusts better to this kind of distribution. The
 452 I_{BS} is obtained from the quotient of geometric means of IRC.

453

454 For the calculation of the combined uncertainty of $I_{BS}(i)$ the expression 5 is applied following the procedure
 455 suggested by CSN (Romero et al., 2003).

456

$$457 \quad u_{I_{BS}(i)} = I_{BS}(i) \sqrt{\frac{u_{RBE}^2}{\langle IRC_{RBE} \rangle_{GM}^2} + \frac{u_i^2}{\langle IRC_i \rangle_{GM}^2}} \quad (6)$$

458

459 Where u_{RBE} and u_i are the uncertainty of geometric means of IRC_{RBE} and IRC_i respectively.

460

461 Table 5 shows the application of I_{BS} to the values obtained in this work in the lower adjacent enclosure
 462 ADE-L (basements) and in the upper adjacent enclosure ADE-U (first floors). The I_{BS} index takes values
 463 less than unity when IRC corresponds to building enclosures in a storey lower than the RBE storey, while
 464 in the case of upper building enclosures the opposite occurs.

465

466 Therefore, by applying the I_{BS} , it is proposed to standardise the methodology of data processing for the
 467 preparation of maps, being able to compensate, when necessary, for the variability of boundary conditions
 468 in which the measurement can be realised when information on the RBE of the building is not available.
 469 The I_{BS} index allows to correct the values obtained in adjacent building enclosures to the one in which the
 470 proposed pan-European map indicates that measurement should be carried out.

471

Table 5. I_{BS} of lower adjacent building enclosures (basement) and upper (first floors) in study area.

	ADE-L (basement)	ADE-U (first floor)
Number of samples	17	61
Geometric mean of $IRC_{ADE, (u_{ADE})}$	121 (2.1) Bq/m ³	74 (2.1) Bq/m ³
Geometric mean of $IRC_{RBE, (u_{RBE})}$	95 (2.0) Bq/m ³	96 (2.2) Bq/m ³
Building Storey Index, $I_{BS} (u_{BS})$	0.79 (0.02)	1.31 (0.05)

472

473

474 Most of the buildings considered are exclusively single-family homes and those with a basement are
 475 generally used as a garage. Buildings with a collective garage below ground floor with a forced ventilation
 476 system should not be extrapolated the value I_{BS-L} without having a specific study which analyses the
 477 appropriateness of its application to these cases.

478

479 5.2 *Ground floor in contact or without direct contact with the ground*

480

481 To better assess the influence of the building typology, especially the contact between the envelope and the
 482 ground, the results of IRC levels obtained for the two categories of RBE defined in table 3 of this article in
 483 both municipalities are analysed separately. In table 6 it is observed that, although both categories can be
 484 considered ground floor according to their definition in the pan-European map (Elío et al., 2019), there are

485 certain discrepancies in the results that can characterise their behaviour. A difference of 14% between the
 486 geometric means of both categories I and II can be observed, increasing to 28% when UTB results are
 487 considered.

488

Table 6. Statistical results of categories I and II RBE of buildings in study areas

	Category I	Category II	Sub-category II-B
Number of Samples	110	28	22
Geometric mean (Geometric Standard deviation)	88 (2.4) Bq/m ³	77 (2.0) Bq/m ³	83 (1.9) Bq/m ³
Upper tolerance bound (UTB)	309 Bq/m³	241 Bq/m³	264 Bq/m³

489

490 Related to this result, it is important to consider that among the buildings in category II, a Sub-category
 491 identified as II-AC in table 3 is included, consisting in those buildings with an air-chamber system between
 492 the ground floor slab and the ground. This kind of building is common in the higher area of La Laguna
 493 where single family homes predominate. This air-chamber solution is adopted in buildings trying to avoid
 494 damp on the walls as a consequence of a high humidity in the ground due to the rainy climate of this area.
 495 It is relevant to note that CTE recommends the application of an air-chamber system as a solution in order
 496 to reduce radon levels in new buildings (Ministerio de Fomento, 2019).

497

498 It appears logical to study the effects of this kind of system in the statistical analysis which is necessary to
 499 determine the risk levels caused by indoor radon gas. In the samples studied, there are 6 cases of building
 500 enclosures with air-chamber systems which report a geometric mean of 58 Bq/m³. This fact supposes that
 501 the difference between geometric means of Category I and the set of Sub-Category II-B (Category II
 502 discounting results from Sub-category II-AC) is reduced to less than half. It could be concluded a certain
 503 coherence between the results of categories I and II, so that it can be concluded that this differentiation is
 504 not necessary. Moreover, the important decline of geometric mean of the set Sub-category II-AC confirms
 505 the advisability of the remediation prescribed by the CTE. Going further, it could be concluded that
 506 measurements realised in air-chambered buildings can be considered anomalous from a statistical point of
 507 view when the radon exposure level of a building is being determined given its effectiveness against IRC.

508 Air-chambered enclosures can obtain low results despite being on radon prone ground, and this fact distorts
509 the statistical analysis.

510

511 As has been discussed above, in order to obtain better quality information in the field, data filtering has
512 been carried out. This consists of excluding the cases in which the buildings have air-chambered enclosures
513 from the analysis to avoid the mentioned distortion caused by this architectural solution.

514

515 *5.3 Analysis of influence in IRC of geological code and TGR*

516

517 The second variable analysed in this work is the geology of the ground where the buildings are sited related
518 to its radiological and geochemical characteristics. In this work, an identification of different codes of
519 lithologies has been realised with the help of IDECanarias Geological and Geotechnical Maps, as well as
520 the work of Losada et al. (2013) concerning the geochemical characteristics of Canary rocks. In a
521 complementary way, TGR measurements have been realised as an indicator tool of radon gas presence in
522 soils. García-Talavera and López-Acevedo (2019) assert that the correlation between TGR and IRC in
523 dwellings is certainly weak but qualitatively significant. Quindós et al. (2008) concluded that gamma
524 radiation can only be used as a qualitative indicator of high IRC levels rather than a quantitative IRC
525 predictor, and then it can be used to obtain a first approximation for the identification of radon prone areas.

526

527 **Geological code**

528

529 Figures 2 and 3 show the locations of buildings with the IRC results in RBE obtained chromatically
530 differentiated by codes over a lithological map. The results have been graphically divided into different
531 ranges (below 100 Bq/m³, between 100 and 200 Bq/m³, between 200 and 300 Bq/m³, and over 300 Bq/m³).

532 There is a total of 79 results in RBE of buildings located in La Laguna discounting those with air-chamber
533 systems, 37 of them located on basic geology (Code B) and the other 42 located on clayey soils (Code C).

534 On the other hand, Telde have 53 results in RBE of buildings sited on basic geology, so that a unique Code
535 B is considered.

536

537

538

539

Figure 3. Map of IRC results in La Laguna coloured by geological code.

540

541

542

Figure 4. Map of IRC results in Telde coloured by geological code.

543

Figure 3 shows that the highest results are predominantly in Code C areas of the municipality of La Laguna.

544

In fact, all results over 300 Bq/m³ belong to Code C. In the case of the municipality of Telde (figure 4) it is

545 not distinguished as an area where the highest results are predominant, but these points are distributed along
 546 the map without a specific area with higher density. However, it can be observed that lower ranges of IRC
 547 are predominant in Code B areas from both municipalities.
 548

549

550

Figure 5. Box and whiskers graphs of IRC results in study areas differentiated by codes

551

552 Figures 5a and 5b show IRC results from Telde and La Laguna respectively, identifying geological codes
 553 B and C. It can be confirmed that geological codes B (basic rocks) from both municipalities have a very
 554 similar behaviour with low values of IRC, observing only four results slightly above 300 Bq/m³ in the case
 555 of Telde, while higher results are found in geological code C from La Laguna, where clayey soils are
 556 extended.

557

558 The application of Mann-Whitney U-Test reveals that there are differences between IRC measured in Code
 559 B and Code C (p-value = 0.00). Values of IRC obtained in each code B and C describe a log-normal
 560 distribution (Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test with Lilliefors correction, p-value = 0.20 for Code B and Shapiro-
 561 Wilks test, p-value = 0.65 for Code C) with heterogeneous variances (Levene's test, p-value = 0.00).

562

563

564 **Terrestrial gamma radiation**

565

566 As has been indicated above, in this work a methodology has been established consisting of designing a
 567 gamma radiation measurements campaign carried out in the proximity of the same locations where IRC
 568 measurements were taken in both municipalities. Applying this methodology, the aim was to obtain a
 569 quantifiable information about the influence of geological characteristics of the underlying ground on IRC.
 570 The CSN in its Technical Report Cartography of radon potential in Spain (García-Talavera and López-
 571 Acevedo, 2019) proposes using the level of gamma radiation as a variable that allows a first approximation
 572 to be made to identify the geographical areas most exposed to radon gas. In this way, the territory is divided
 573 into three categories depending on whether their radiation level is below 66 nGy/h (~ 7.5 µR/h) for the first
 574 category, between that value and 123 nGy/h (~ 14.0 µR/h) for the second and higher values for the third.
 575 García Talavera et al. (2019) concludes that the level of 66 nGy/h is a very reliable limit to determine that
 576 the regions with lower rates do not constitute priority action areas for radon exposure.
 577 Figure 6 shows TGR ambient dose results regarding IRC in La Laguna and Telde respectively, identifying
 578 geologies chromatically.
 579

580
 581 **Figure 6.** Results of IRC in RBE of buildings from study areas according to TGR. Black squares marks indicate Code B and red
 582 circles marks denote Code C. Vertical lines correspond to the cut-off proposed by Talavera et al. (2013) (66 nGy/h) and the cut-off
 583 proposed in this work (71 nGy/h).
 584
 585 Considering these ranges, it can be observed in figures 5a and 5b that both in Telde and in La Laguna those
 586 points that show TGR lower than 66 nGy/h have an IRC lower than 300 Bq/m³, except only two cases in
 587 Telde which slightly exceed this limit (305 Bq/m³ and 351 Bq/m³). In line with this, in table 7 it can be
 588 observed that the geometric mean of IRC in this range gives a result of 65 Bq/m³. This geometric mean is

589 lower than that obtained by García-Talavera in 181 municipalities from mainland Spain with TGR lower
 590 than 66 nGy/h whose value is 70 Bq/m³. On the other hand, no point from Telde or La Laguna exceeds the
 591 cut-off of 123 nGy/h, so that the whole set of samples evaluated would belong to the two first ranges,
 592 obtaining a UTB of 237 Bq/m³ for those points with TGR lower than 66 nGy/h and 360 Bq/m³ for the rest.
 593 The application of a Mann-Whitney U-Test shows that there are differences between measurements of IRC
 594 belonging to the two ranges considered (p-value = 0.00).

595

Table 7. Statistical results of IRC measured in RBE by ranges of TGR values according to CSN

	Low TGR (< 66 nGy/h)	Intermediate TGR (66 – 123 nGy/h)	High TGR (>123 nGy/h)
Samples	57	73	0
Geometric mean (Geometric stand- ard deviation)	65 (2.3) Bq/m ³	108 (2.2) Bq/m ³	--
Upper tolerance bound (UTB)	237	360	--

596

597 In the paper of Talavera et al. (2013) the TGR cut-off 66 nGy/h is linked to a geometric mean of IRC 70
 598 Bq/m³ in the study area. However, these limits proposed by the CSN respond to a geological reality typical
 599 of continental Spain (mainland Spain), which is very different from the Canarian geology markedly
 600 characterised by its intraplate volcanic origin (Carracedo et al., 2002). In this work, the value of TGR which
 601 gives exactly this geometric mean is 70.5 nGy/h. This leads us to propose a limit of 71 nGy / h for our study
 602 area. The observed behaviour in the graphs of figures 5a and 5b around the value 71 nGy/h, makes to infer
 603 that using this cut-off allows for establishing ranges of TGR which adjust better to the results obtained in
 604 the current study. As can be observed, only 4 of the 97 points in which a TGR lower than the analysed limit
 605 is observed slightly exceed 300 Bq/m³, offering a geometric mean of 71 Bq/m³, while those points which
 606 exceed 71 nGy/h show a more disparate behaviour obtaining a geometric mean of 169 Bq/m³. As can be
 607 seen in Table 8, this fact translates into obtaining an UTB of 212 Bq/m³ in values from the first range, and
 608 UTB of 712 Bq/m³ in values from the second. For these new ranges, the existence of different ranges of
 609 IRC measurements was also verified (Mann-Whitney U-test, p-value = 0.00).

610

611 As explained in section 4.7 of this paper, the shortage of cases exceeding 71 nGy/h in both analysed
 612 municipalities makes it not statistically advisable to establish several different ranges for this population,
 613 since the consequent loss of samples in each range would distort the results.

614

Table 8. Statistical results of IRC measured in RBE by ranges of TGR values

	Low TGR (< 71 nGy/h)	High TGR (\geq 71 nGy/h)
Samples	101	29
Geometric mean	71	169
Geometric Standard deviation	2.1	2.4
Upper tolerance bound (UTB)	212	712

615

616 **6 CONCLUSIONS**

617 Two indoor radon and terrestrial gamma radiation measurement campaigns have been carried out in the
 618 study areas considered (municipalities of the Canary Islands: La Laguna and Telde), matching the phys-
 619 ical location of the measurement points in both campaigns.

620 A definition of the RBE has been proposed with the intention of achieving greater precision when select-
 621 ing the enclosures in which the measurements are carried out in order to provide greater uniformity of
 622 criteria in the elaboration of maps.

623 The IRC field campaign has been designed in such a way that whenever possible two passive detectors
 624 have been placed in the RBE and another one in the vertically contiguous enclosure, the upper one when
 625 the RBE was in contact with the ground and the lower one when it was not.

626 To study the influence of the type of soil in which a building is located on the IRC, a simplified coding
 627 has been defined based on the geochemical and radiometric characteristics of the soils in the study areas
 628 that classify them into acidic rocks (Code A), basic (Code B), clayey (Code C) and marine detrital sedi-
 629 ments (Code D).

630 The main results obtained are the following:

- 631 1) It has been observed that the UTB calculated for a study area can give disparate values depend-
 632 ing on whether rooms located on the upper or lower storey are predominantly chosen. As a

633 result of the implementation of this methodology, a I_{BS} was obtained that would allow normal-
634 ising measurements taken in rooms from storeys which are not ground floor, when this infor-
635 mation is available in the initiatives carried out to define radon prone areas.

636 2) On the other hand, it has been found that there are constructive solutions that drastically reduce
637 radon gas access to the building, even though it sits on land with a high concentration of radon,
638 such as an air-chamber between the floor and the ground. The results obtained in the air-cham-
639 bered enclosures can be considered statistically anomalous, and their use in calculating the UTB
640 of the geographical area under study is not recommended.

641 3) La Laguna is fundamentally divided into two codes (Code B and Code C), while Telde in its
642 entirety is in Code B. In this study, it is shown that buildings that sit on basic rocks or soils
643 derived directly from these rocks present significantly low IRC results. In clayey soils of La
644 Laguna (Code C), due to their formation process in which a higher concentration of natural
645 radioisotopes accumulates than in the rocks from which they come, buildings withstand signif-
646 icantly higher IRC levels.

647 4) After analysing the TGR campaign carried out in the vicinity of the points where the IRC has
648 been measured, it is observed that in these municipalities the TGR can be used as a categorical
649 variable to define radon risk areas. Considering the limits of TGR established by CSN to delimit
650 radon prone areas it can be observed that values below 66 nGy/h have a UTB of 237 Bq/m³, so
651 these would not be priority action areas (<300 Bq/m³). However, CSN links this limit to a geo-
652 metric mean of IRC of 70 Bq/m³, so it is also possible to define a TGR cut-off of 71 nGy/h
653 around which, in addition, a certain ordering of radon levels is distinguished. Below this cut-
654 off, the IRC results are concentrated in geological code B (Telde and part of La Laguna), ob-
655 taining for this population a UTB of 212 Bq/m³, and therefore a low risk level for radon gas
656 exposure. Buildings located in code C in La Laguna whose UTB exceeds 700 Bq/m³ exhibit
657 TGR values above 71 nGy/h.

658 5) The proposed methodology can be applied in other Canary geographic areas. Increasing the
659 density of samples, the results here presented can be generalized to the entire archipelago and
660 help to define the radon prone areas with more precision.

661

662 **7 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT**

663 This work has been financed by Government of the Canary Islands (Consejería de obras públicas, trans-
664 porte y vivienda) through the collaboration agreement with the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
665 for a “Proposal for a new zoning to predict the level of risk derived from the presence of radon concentra-
666 tions inside buildings”. On the other hand, the authors would like to acknowledge the collaboration of the
667 Telde City Council's environmental department (Concejalía de Medioambiente).

668 **8 REFERENCES**

669

- 670 Arnedo, M.A., Rubiano, J.G., Alonso, H., Tejera, A., González, A., González, J., Gil, J.M., Rodríguez,
671 R., Martel, P., Bolivar, J.P., 2017. Mapping natural radioactivity of soils in the Eastern Canary
672 Islands. *J. Env. Radioact*, 166-2 242-258. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
- 673 Barnet, I., Fojtíková, I., 2008. Soil gas radon, indoor radon and gamma dose rate in CZ: Contribution to
674 geostatistical methods for European atlas of natural radiations. *Radiat. Prot. Dosimetry* 130, 81–84.
675 <https://doi.org/10.1093/rpd/ncn107>
- 676 Bochicchio, F., Campos-Venuti, G., Piermattei, S., Nuccetelli, C., Risica, S., Tommasino, L., Torri, G.,
677 Magnoni, M., Agnesod, G., Sgorbati, G., Bonomi, M., Minach, L., Trotti, F., Malisan, M.R.,
678 Maggiolo, S., Gaidolfi, L., Giannardi, C., Rongoni, A., Lombardi, M., Cherubini, G., D’Ostilio, S.,
679 Cristofaro, C., Pugliese, M., Martucci, V., Crispino, A., Cuzzocrea, P., Santamaria, A.S., Cappai,
680 M., 2005. Annual average and seasonal variations of residential radon concentration for all the
681 Italian Regions. *Radiat. Meas.* 40, 686–694. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2004.12.023>
- 682 Bossew, P., 2015. Mapping the Geogenic Radon Potential and Estimation of Radon Prone Areas in
683 Germany. *Radiat. Emerg. Med.* 4, 13–20.
- 684 Carracedo, J.C., Pérez Torrado, F.J., Ancochea, E., Meco, J., Hernán, F., Cubas, C.R., Casillas, R.,
685 Rodríguez-Badiola, E., Ahijado, A., 2002. Cenozoic Volcanism II: the Canary Islands., in: *The*
686 *Geological Society London*.
- 687 Cinelli, G., Tondeur, F., Dehandschutter, B., 2011. Development of an indoor radon risk map of the
688 Walloon region of Belgium, integrating geological information. *Environ. Earth Sci.* 62, 809–819.
689 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-010-0568-5>
- 690 Collignan, B., Le Ponner, E., Mandin, C., 2016. Relationships between indoor radon concentrations,

691 thermal retrofit and dwelling characteristics. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 165, 124–130.
692 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2016.09.013>

693 Elío, J., Cinelli, G., Bossew, P., Gutiérrez-Villanueva, J.L., Tollefsen, T., De Cort, M., Nogarotto, A.,
694 Braga, R., 2019. The first version of the Pan-European Indoor Radon Map. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst.*
695 *Sci.* 19, 2451–2464. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-19-2451-2019>

696 Elío, J., Crowley, Q., Scanlon, R., Hodgson, J., Long, S., 2017. Logistic regression model for detecting
697 radon prone areas in Ireland. *Sci. Total Environ.* 599–600, 1317–1329.
698 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.05.071>

699 European Commission, 2019. European atlas of Natural Radiation.

700 Font, L., 1997. Radon generation, entry and accumulation indoors. Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona.

701 Frutos Vázquez, B., 2009. Estudio experimental sobre la efectividad y la viabilidad de distintas
702 soluciones constructivas para reducir la concentración de gas radón en edificaciones. Universidad
703 Politécnica de Madrid.

704 García-Talavera, M., García-Pérez, A., Rey, C., Ramos, L., 2013. Mapping radon-prone areas using γ -
705 radiation dose rate and geological information. *J. Radiol. Prot.* 33, 605–620.
706 <https://doi.org/10.1088/0952-4746/33/3/605>

707 García-Talavera, M., López-Acevedo, F.J., 2019. Cartografía del potencial de radón de España. Colección
708 Inf. Técnicos del Cons. Segur. Nucl.

709 García-Talavera San Miguel, M., Martín-Matarranz, J.L., Gil de Mingo, R., García Cadierno, J.P., Suárez
710 Mahou, E., 2013. El mapa predictivo de exposición al radón en España. Colección Inf. Técnicos
711 38.2013 141, 40–42.

712 Health Protection Agency, 2009. Report of the independent Advisory Group on Ionising Radiation.

713 Hintenlang, D., Al-ahmady, K., 1992. Pressure Differentials for Radon Entry Coupled to Periodic
714 Atmospheric Pressure Variations. *Munskgaard* 1992, 208–215.

715 Ielsch, G., Cushing, M.E., Combes, P., Cuney, M., 2010. Mapping of the geogenic radon potential in
716 France to improve radon risk management: Methodology and first application to region Bourgogne.
717 *J. Environ. Radioact.* 101, 813–820. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2010.04.006>

718 IGFAE, 2019. Información general sobre el gas radón [WWW Document]. Univ. Santiago Compost.

719 Kemski, J., Klingel, R., Siehl, A., Valdivia-Manchego, M., 2009. From radon hazard to risk prediction-
720 based on geological maps, soil gas and indoor measurements in Germany. *Environ. Geol.* 56, 1269–

721 1279. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00254-008-1226-z>

722 Kemski, J., Siehl, A., Stegemann, R., Valdivia-Manchego, M., 2001. Mapping the geogenic radon
723 potential in Germany. *Sci. Total Environ.* 272, 217–230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048->
724 9697(01)00696-9

725 Losada, A., Peña, A., Viñas, R., Hernández, L., 2013. Caracterización geomecánica de rocas . Parámetros
726 mecánico-deformacionales y geoquímicos. Gobierno de Canarias.

727 Meeker, W.Q., Hahn, G.J., Escobar, L.A., 1991. *Statistical intervals: a guide for practitioners*. Wiley, cop.

728 Ministerio de Fomento, 2019. Documento Básico de Salubridad HS. Boletín Of. del Estado 2013, 1–129.

729 Ministerio de Presidencia y Administraciones Territoriales, 2018. Proyecto de Real Decreto, por el que se
730 aprueba el Reglamento sobre protección de la salud contra los riesgos derivados de la exposición a
731 las radiaciones ionizantes. Boletín Of. del Estado.

732 Odeh, R.E., Owen, D.B., 1980. Tables for normal tolerance limits, sampling plans, and screening.

733 Quindós, L.S., Fernández, P.L., Sainz, C., Fuente, I., Nicolás, J., Quindós, L., Arteché, J., 2008. Indoor
734 radon in a Spanish region with different gamma exposure levels. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 99, 1544–
735 1547. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2007.12.011>

736 R. W. Le Maitre, 2002. *Igneous Rock. A Classification and Glossary of Terms*. Recommendations of the
737 International Union of Geological Sciences Subcommittee on the Systematics of Igneous Rocks,
738 Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>

739 Robayna Duque, B.E., 2002. Radón en viviendas de las Islas Canarias occidentales. Distribución
740 geográfica y dosimetría. Universidad de La Laguna.

741 Romero, M.L., Fernández, M.C., Gascó, C., García-Toraño, E., González, J.A., Heras, M.C., Montero,
742 M., Núñez-Lagos, R., 2003. Procedimiento para la evaluación de incertidumbres en la
743 determinación de la radiactividad ambiental. Colección Inf. Técnicos.

744 Sainz-Fernandez, C., Fernandez-Villar, A., Fuente-Merino, I., Gutierrez-Villanueva, J.L., Martin-
745 Matarranz, J.L., Garcia-Talavera, M., Casal-Ordas, S., Quindós-Poncela, L.S., 2014. The Spanish
746 indoor radon mapping strategy. *Radiat. Prot. Dosimetry* 162, 58–62.
747 <https://doi.org/10.1093/rpd/ncu218>

748 Suárez-Mahou, E., Fernández-Amigot, Á., Moro, M., García-Pomar, D., Moreno, J., Lanaja, J., 2000.
749 INT-04-02 Proyecto Marna. Mapa de radiación gamma natural.pdf. Colección Inf. Técnicos Cons.
750 Segur. Nucl.

751 World Health Organization, 2015. Manual de la OMS sobre Radón en interiores.

752